

Automated Classification of Aberrant p53 Immunohistochemical Patterns in Cutaneous Squamous Cell Carcinoma Using Machine Learning

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February 2026

Abstract

Cutaneous Squamous Cell Carcinoma (cSCC) is among the most common prevalent skin malignancies. A significant event in cSCC is TP53 gene disruption. TP53 gene produces p53 protein, a tumor suppressor protein that repairs damaged DNA and regulates cell-cycle. Because TP53 alteration is frequently observed in cSCC, p53 immunohistochemistry (IHC) is widely used in pathology as a marker: it identifies whether the nuclear pattern of a p53 is normal or abnormal (overexpression or complete absence). This study introduced a patch-based model that was trained on a public cohort UCSF 2021 to classify p53 IHC images as normal pattern or abnormal. The model illustrated high results on a patch-based test (AUC=0.9855 and ACC=0.9697), but demonstrated a lower score on a slide-level test (AUC=0.9573 and ACC=0.7742) due to slide heterogeneity and confusing artifacts.

1 Introduction

TP53 gene encodes the P53 protein — a tumor suppressor that regulates the cell cycle and restores damaged DNA. When this gene is disrupted, cells can accumulate mutations, long ultraviolet (UV) exposure causing a mutational pressure, leading to a cutaneous squamous cell carcinoma (cSCC), most known as cancer. Using the public cohort from the dataset UCSF 2021, we found out that TP53 mutations were present in 66.27% tumors (55 out of 83). The most dominant type of mutation was missense variant (65.43%). This study shows that TP53 alteration is not a rare case in cSCC.

In recent decades pathologists often use immunohistochemistry (IHC) to detect any mutation in the p53 pathway. IHC evaluates nuclear patterns and distinguishes normal pattern from abnormal: strong overexpression or complete emptiness. However, identifying these patterns and verifying them is not always straightforward. Especially for general pathologists and with limited resources.

That is precisely why this project matters. Our project developed a patch-based model that classifies nuclear patterns just as TP53 IHC. Whole sized images are sliced into many patches 64x64 each. The model was trained to identify whether the nuclear pattern is normal or abnormal. For local clinics without proper technology, these findings suggest the potential utility in resource-limited clinics.

2 Methods

The data in this study were obtained from the publicly available cohort UCSF (2021) cutaneous squamous cell carcinoma. The data was initially described by Chang and Shain (2021).

Using the genomic annotations mentioned above, we computed the frequency of TP53 mutations across the cohort, and indicated the most widespread variant of TP53 mutation. In addition, we built a convolutional neural network (CNN), based on the ResNet-18 architecture, that was trained using UCSF cohort cutaneous squamous cell carcinoma (2021) to identify cell condition: whether it has mutations or not, with 1 input and output layers and 16 hidden layers. Only cases with available P53 IHC were included in this study. The architecture also includes an initial 7x7 convolutional layer with stride 2 and 4 residual blocks with increasing feature channels.

Whole-sized images were first split into many smaller slides. All slides were resized to 224x224 pixels to conduct a precise analysis on each region of the cell. To prevent the model from the data leakage — meaning the model would not cheat while identifying mutations — the slides were divided into training set, validation set, and testing set, where each set consists of different slides: 70% training set, 15% validation set, and 15% testing set.

The training of the model was conducted using following configuration:

1. Optimizer: AdamW
2. Learning rate: 3×10^{-4}
3. Batch size: 32
4. Number of epochs: 10

After completing training and testing the checkpoint was set, and the AUC, ACC, confusion Matrix, Precision, and recall were saved for model evaluation.

The dataset itself consists of binary labels corresponding to TP53 mutations: mutated and non-mutated. During the test the distribution at the patch level was imbalanced, meaning the amount of abnormal expression pathed was greater than the amount of normal patterns. Class imbalance was considered during the model evaluation.

Additionally, most clinics made their decisions at the slide-level rather than the patch-level. Therefore, we generated slide-level classifications. We combined all patches' probabilities using mean aggregation: $(1/N) * \sum_{i=1}^N p(i)$. If the result is lower than 0.5, then the slide score would be classified as non-mutated.

All experiments were conducted using the Python extension — PyTorch. The training part was performed in CPU hardware.

3 Results

To provide context for abnormal p53 pattern correlation with the cSCC, we analyzed a public cohort (UCSF 2021) and created figures using data from cBioPortal. Among 83 samples, 55 of them were TP53-altered, thereby illustrating a strong correlation between TP53 mutation and cSCC (66.265%). The TP53 mutation was mostly dominated by missense variants (65.4%), nonsense

(11.1%), silent (6.2%), and intronic variants (5%). We elaborated a TP53 gene mutation classifier, as well as provided the score of patch-level and slide-level predictions. Across 66 patches the model demonstrated high patch-based accuracy of 0.9697, and AUC was 0.9573. Recall for each pattern (abnormal and normal) was 0.945 and 0.9773 respectively, corresponding to a strong quality control in discriminating TP53 patterns, with only 2 false positives among 66 different patches. Slide-level performance (31 slides) achieved the accuracy of 0.7742 and AUC=0.9573. Recall for each pattern was 0.9767 for abnormal and 0.611 (11/18) for normal pattern, underlying that the only issue is primarily classifying normal patterns as abnormal. The mistake is mostly lack of quality control, as several slides contained mixed labels across patches.

The figure below illustrates a TP53 gene alteration frequency in a cSCC cohort among 83 samples. As seen, 55 out of 83 TP53 genes were disrupted, thereby illustrating a strong correlation between TP53 mutation and cSCC (0.6625).

Second figure demonstrates TP53 mutation most common variants by classification: missense, nonsense, frameshift, and splice), where most of the mutations were missense variants (52/83)

Figure 1: Distribution of TP53 mutation variants in the UCSF cSCC cohort.

4 Discussion

TP53 gene encodes p53 protein — a tumor suppressor that restores damaged DNA and regulates cell-cycle. (Tornesello, 2025). TP53 disruption is a really crucial part in pathology, consistent with high UV exposure and mutational burden typical of sun-exposed skin. That being said, this biological process makes p53 IHC perfect marker, because p53 wild type tends to express weaker nuclear coloring (normal pattern), however, when TP53 experiences alteration, it expresses abnormal patterns:

1. Diffuse overexpression — too many nuclei are colored.
2. Complete absence — almost no nuclei are colored.

The model’s high scores in AUC and ACC on patch based (0.9855 and 0.9697) suggests that it learned to identify whether the gene is mutated or not. Although we got 0.7742 in slide-level ACC, it demonstrates that TP53 gene is heterogeneous, meaning that if a patch-based model could easily recognize pattern, it is challenging for slide-level model to predict the pattern, since the whole slide contains many mixtures of tumor, stroma, keratin, and other parts of the cell. The slide-level confusion matrix reveals that the model achieved a perfect score in identifying abnormal patterns (13/13), but struggles with the normal slides due to mixed or influenced by technical factors that confuses the model. It suggests that the next step in enhancing a model is to train it with ambiguous slides, or include another variant of pattern — mixed, which contains both normal and abnormal patterns.

5 Limitations

This model was developed to classify P53 IHC patterns in cutaneous squamous cell carcinoma for research only. The model does not make a diagnosis and can not replace a visit by a pathologist, instead, it is a supporting tool for clinics.

Second, the dataset size is relatively small, however, the patch-based training increases the number of training samples, leading to a higher accuracy.

Third, the analysis and the model itself were conducted using a single publicly available cohort from UCSF (2021). No external dataset was used, therefore, the model's accuracy was not tested on different institutions and scanners.

Fourth, some heterogenous slides contain artifacts, including background noise, tissue folding, and color shifts. As a result, the model demonstrated reduced accuracy rate, meaning that the model is sensitive to such confounding factors.

Fifth, the model's validation set is not yet tested in real clinic workflow. In other words, the model has not been evaluated under real-life diagnosis uncertainty.

Acknowledgments

The author thanks Dr. Madina for supervision and guidance. This writing utilized publicly opened cutaneous squamous cell carcinoma cohort UCSF (2021) via cBioPortal. The original investigators are acknowledged for data access

Data Availability

The data analyzed in this study were taken from the UCSF (2021) cutaneous squamous cell carcinoma (cSCC) cohort using cBioPortal (Chang and Shain, 2021.). The UCSF cutaneous squamous cell carcinoma cohort is publicly available via cBioPortal. The scripts, the model architecture, the training code are publicly available at: <https://github.com/Rahuilan/p53-IHC-classifier>

6 References

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